

Role of disaster management agencies in disaster assessment in Bangladesh

Abstract:

Bangladesh is the most disaster-prone country in the world. Different disaster management agencies work for disaster assessment at various level across the country. Bangladesh government established the structure of disaster management committee as part of assessment, preparedness and response. The study reveals how the different government organizations, international organizations and non-government organizations (NGOs) closely work coordinated way in disaster assessment in order to risk reduction. The assessment study in Dhaka North City Corporation (DNCC) also shows urban disaster resilience, how the risk situation changes constantly in urban context. The study also revealed the multiple actors involvement in disaster assessment during the flood of 1998. The assessment brought some statistical table of loss and affected people that shows in references and appendix. Assessment of vulnerability in agriculture sector during disaster brought past disaster phenomena data and shows the risk trend as part of disaster assessment.

Introduction:

Bangladesh and its people have been one of the worst victims of natural disasters from time immemorial. Conversely, facing and learning to live with natural disasters are equally an ancient preoccupation of Bangladeshi people. Disaster management in independent Bangladesh has undergone a complex process of development. While it received its impetus from concrete challenges faced at home, it also received inputs from developments, institutions and policies outside Bangladesh. In the process, Bangladesh has developed a workable system of disaster management that includes a set of mechanisms and processes, as well as a whole range of ways and means for the management of disasters. (1) Some disaster management agencies are playing vital role to disaster risk reduction through disaster assessment in Bangladesh. The National Plan for Disaster Management (NPDM 2016–2020) of Bangladesh was prepared by the author for the Ministry of Disaster Management and Relief (MoDMR), supported by the United Nations Development Programme (UNDP), and it is aligned with international frameworks including the Sendai Framework for Disaster Risk Reduction (SFDRR). As a disaster management agencies they are playing main role for disaster assessment in order to risk reduction. (2)

National and international NGOs have important role in disaster assessment in Bangladesh like DFID, OXFAM GB, USAID, Care International and Caritas. The Bangladesh Red Crescent Society (BDRCS) and various donor agencies play important roles. The Cyclone Preparedness Program (CPP) was established in 1972 following the devastating cyclone of 1970, under an agreement between the BDRCS and the government of Bangladesh, with an aim to undertake effective cyclone preparedness measures in the coastal areas. CPP, under the BDRCS, has a joint

management structure, with two committees, like a 7-member Policy Committee headed by the Minister of MoFDM, and a 15-member Implementation Board led by the Secretary of the MoFDM. Now the CPP has about 33,120 trained volunteers, including 5,520 women.

The following structure of disaster management committee maintain by government, NGOs and partnership approach. It's an essential part of assessment, preparedness and response.

1. National Disaster Management Council 2. Inter-ministerial Disaster Management Coordination Committee 3. National Disaster Management Advisory Committee 4. District Level Disaster Management Committee 5. Upazilla Level Disaster Management Committee 6. Union Level Disaster Management Committee

Assessment of urban disaster resilience in Dhaka North City Corporation (DNCC):

The assessment covers urban disaster resilience index (URDI), physical resilience, Social resilience, institutional resilience and natural resilience. Disaster resilience in urban context is an integration of infrastructural, institutional, social, and economic resilience.

As compared to the data in 2010 when the overall UDRI score was 2.35 [12], resilience level increased in 2016. Particularly, the comparison shows remarkable improvement in physical and economic resilience where physical resilience score rose from 2.90 in 2010 to 3.37 in 2016 and economic resilience from 1.64 to 2.23.

Data shows in Table 1: This increase can be observed in our daily life that the city has achieved significant infrastructural development to ensure access to electricity, water, and roads for its residents and Bangladesh having achieved around a 6% of annual economic growth that gained more attention in global economy. Large part of the country's GDP is produced in the capital. However, on the other hand, natural, social, and institutional resilience score dropped from 2.51 to 2.37, 2.56 to 2.53, and 2.15 to 2.11 respectively, which kept overall resilience score increase as low as 7 % since 2010 in spite of the remarkable improvement in physical and economic resilience. It indicates that holistic approach is essential as the assessment clearly shows only improvement of only infrastructure is not enough to accelerate the score. Risk situation changes constantly and it requires continuous effort to achieve higher resilience. (3)

Multiple actor's involvement in 1998 flood:

In 1998, this flood was the most prolonged flood. During that time multiple actors was involved for preparedness and assessment for damages or losses by this flood. The multiple actors are: Ministry of Environment and Forest, Ministry of Agriculture, Ministry of Food, Disaster Management and Relief, Ministry of Fisheries and Livestock, Ministry of Land, Ministry of Planning Commination , Ministry of Water Resources,

Local Government Division, MOLGRD&C, Ministry of Civil Aviation and Tourism, Ministry of Chittagong Hill Tracts Affairs Planning Commission, Bangladesh Water Development Board, Bangladesh Forest Research Institute, Bangladesh Bureau of Statistics, Bangladesh Meteorology Department, Disaster Management Bureau, Department of Environment, Department of Fisheries, Department of Agriculture, Extension Local Government Engineering Department, Space Research and Remote Sensing Organization, Water Resources Planning Organization, Bangladesh Agriculture Research Council, Bangladesh Institute of Development Studies, Institute of Water Modeling, Barind Multi-purpose Development Authority.

Estimates of Losses and Damage in the Bangladesh Flood of 1988 shows in Table 2: Reference (4)

Damage assessment caused by cyclone SIDR: Ministry of food and disaster management.

Cyclone SIDR that hit Bangladesh coast on 15 November 2007 caused death of 3199 people with huge economic loss estimated as USD 3 billion. Damage assessment report has shown in Table 3. But there are so many cyclone occurred in Bangladesh. Different times assessment done by disaster management agencies. A brief overview shown below in percentage.

Approximately 45 damaging cyclones were reported in the coastal areas of Bangladesh from 1793 to May 1997, thus cyclone frequency during this period averaged once in every 4.5 years. Among which the devastating cyclones occurred in 1961, 1963, 1965, 1966, 1970, 1985 and 1991 and in 1996. Besides, the historic book 'Ain e Akbari' quoted a devastating cyclone in the Barishal region in 1854. The last devastation cyclones that hit Bangladesh occurred respectively 12 November 1970, 29 April 1991 and 15 November 2007. Cyclone in 1970 caused death of 300,000 people with a financial loss of USD 86.4 million. In 1991 cyclone an estimated 131,000 to 139,000 people died, with the majority of those dying being below the age of 10, and a third of them below the age of five; also more women than men died (Talukder and Ahmed, 1992). An estimated 1 million homes were completely destroyed, and a further 1 million damaged. Up to 60% of cattle and 80% of poultry stocks were destroyed and up to 280,000 acres of standing crops destroyed; 740 km of flood embankments were destroyed or badly damaged, exposing 72,000 hectares of rice paddy to salt water intrusion. The floodwaters brought disease and hunger to the survivors. The total economic impact of the cyclone was US\$2.4 to 4.0 billion. (5)

A UNDP report titled 'Reducing Risk of Natural Disasters: A Development Challenge' says that among the Asian countries Bangladesh is highly prone to cyclonic disaster. The report also says, during 1980 to 2000 cyclone caused death of 250 thousand people worldwide, of which 60 percent were in Bangladesh. Although, the Philippines is more vulnerable to cyclone than Bangladesh but cyclonic death is 10 times more in Bangladesh than the Philippines.

Assessment of vulnerability in agricultural sector in disaster:

The trend analysis for 30 years (1984 - 2013) of cropped area in four disaster prone areas shows that the overall cropped area decreased by 1% from 1984 to 2013. It was observed that, in case of drought prone areas, the cropped area of Aus and Aman is decreased by 25%, jute by 61%, wheat, mustard and pulse by 14%. However, the cropped area of Boro crop has increased by 62%. In saline regions, the area under HYV Boro remained static throughout the period because of salinity problems in dry season. In the river flood prone areas, the maximum cropped area was decreased by 25% in case of Aus and the minimum by 13% in the case of vegetables. It was revealed that the Aman cropped area was decreased by about 25%. The maximum cropping intensity was found in drought prone areas, which is followed by flash flood prone, saline prone and river flood prone areas. (6)

To add sum up, disaster management agency played a vital role to contribute the overall management of disaster situation in our country context. Disaster assessment is an integral part of disaster management. It needs to well discipline support to gather all information for mitigating the disaster situation. Different departments of Bangladesh government are playing active role of coordination, supporting assessment, response and recovery. There is no scope of separate thinking to response in disaster. Because the need of disaster situation creates different level support. Assessment is a tool that we have to use in all part of the cycle. There are different tools are using for disaster assessment. If we look at the disaster management agencies role in different published report then we found that they have active role in pre disaster planning, survey and data collection, interpretation, forecasting and reporting and monitoring. The assessment works complete in pre and post disaster phase. The sustainability of disaster risk management depends on how disaster management agencies are playing active role on disaster assessment. Previous year assessment report are also counting to realize the intensity in regarding to current hazards. In this short paper, the draw of attention made on the defining the disaster management agencies and their role on disaster assessment. Due to the page limitation, all the role could not explain well. Every narration has certain references and mostly have taken form google scholars' article.

References and appendix

Table 1: UDRI score in 2010 and 2016

Year	overall	physical	Social	economical	institutional	Natural
2010	2.35	2.90	2.56	1.64	2.15	2.51
2016	2.52	3.37	2.53	2.23	2.11	2.37

Dhaka city administration was divided into Dhaka North City Corporation (DNCC) and Dhaka South City Corporation (DSCC) in 2011 and this study was conducted in 36 wards of DNCC. For the purpose of comparison from 2010, this considers DNCC as representative of the entire city of Dhaka.

Table 2: Estimates of Losses and Damage in the Bangladesh Flood of 1988

Particulars	Quantity
Area flooded (km ²)	89,970
Average duration of floods (days)	34
Number of affected people	45,000,000
Number of deaths	2,379
Rice production lost (million tons)	2.00
Number of cattle lost	172,000
Roads damaged (km)	13,000
Embankments damaged (km)	1,990
Number of bridges and culverts	1,160
damaged Number of affected houses	7,200,000
Number of schools damaged	19,000

Table 3: Damage caused by cyclone SIDR

Particulars Population affected	69,00,000
Total family affected	16,00,000
Death	3199
Missed	1180
Crop land damaged (hector)	16,10,000
Livestock perished	468000
Education Inst. damaged	9,248
Embankment damaged (Km)	614
Roads (both earthen and brick-built) damaged	89,428

Source: Preliminary Assessment by Ministry of Food & Disaster Management, Source New Age on 26.11.07

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About the Author:

The author name is Md. Ziaul Hoque. He has around 11 years job experiences in the development sector. He is now working in an international NGO in Rohingya Refugee Program. He is experienced in WASH, Entrepreneurship, Protection, Tuberculosis program. He has sound experience in project risk management, Monitoring, Evaluation, Accountability and Learning (MEAL) and budgeting. For any query, please reach to myziaul@gmail.com.